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ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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The “I”(s) of the Glitches of this Spectrum

**Insecurities. Insults. Irritations. Imperfections. Incapability.
Influenced. Incorrect. Important.**

Each of us has INSECURITIES about everything we do. About everything we look like. About everything that makes us who we are?

Every one of us received INSULTS from this close-minded society. We all suffered from the distaste of the majority, for we are different, which makes us the enemy.

Each of us controls our IRRITATION toward this society. Because if we let it out, people will wrong us. It will give them more leverage to disregard our feelings and justify their wrong actions.

Every one of us hides our IMPERFECTIONS from the eyes of the world. We hide them because we are scared of being judged. Because we know that this world will not understand. Every one of us is ashamed of our INCAPABILITIES, for we know that this will make the world turn its back and leave us behind. For this will give them more excuse to abandon us.

Every one of us is easily INFLUENCED by the hurtful words of the people of this judgmental community. It gives us so much pain that it changes our view of ourselves.

To those of us who are not aware, to those changed by this society, hear this and remember this always. They are INCORRECT.

To those of us whose mindset degrades themselves, you are INCORRECT.

To those whose confidence is dimmed by this hurtful society, hear this: You are IMPORTANT, and no one has anything to say about that. No one has any rights to disrespect that.

Every insecurity you have, you will overcome someday, and be the best version of you.
Every insult they have said is just an unbiased opinion of their jealousy.

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Every irritation you have is not wrong; however, do not let it devour you. You do not have to change for those who do not appreciate your worth.

Every imperfection you have is not bad or something to be ashamed of. You are imperfect; that is why you improve.

You gain what no one else could because you are not perfect. You try and try and try until you learn how to do things properly because you have such incapability.

You do not need to be influenced by people around you. You are alright the way you are, and you do not need their opinions to know how worthy you are.

The society is wrong to judge our personality, capabilities, and worth.

They are incorrect for saying we are not welcome in this world.

You are important simply because you are who YOU ARE.

You are meant to be BEAUTIFUL, not PERFECT.